
MOMENT OF INERTIA FOR A REGULAR N-DIMENSIONAL POLYGONAL PRISM ABOUT ITS CENTROIDAL AXIS

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the moment of inertia I of regular n-dimensional polygonal prisms about their centroidal axes, deriving formulas for both solid and hollow bodies. It provides a simpler derivation for the moment of inertia for the purpose of introductory experiments, as well as provides a table of values for some standard prisms (Figure 6).

Keywords Moment of Inertia · Rotational Dynamics · Geometric Analysis · Engineering Mathematics

1 Introduction

The moment of inertia is a fundamental quantity in the study of rotational dynamics, characterizing an object's resistance to angular acceleration about a given axis. While the moments of inertia for common geometric shapes such as cylinders and spheres are well-documented, the moments of inertia for more complex shapes or 3D shapes remain less explored. This paper focuses on deriving the moments of inertia for regular n-dimensional polygonal prisms about their centroidal axes.

This paper aims to fill the gap in the literature by providing comprehensive formulas and derivations for these moments of inertia, thereby contributing to a deeper understanding of the rotational properties of these geometric shapes. It is intended as a simpler documentation of theoretical inertia values as a substitute for more complex representations (i.e. inertia tensor) for introductory experiments. Other simple cases may allow for similar steps in their derivation to obtain inertia about different axes for non-prismatic polyhedra.

We begin by revisiting the well-known case of the cylindrical prism, which can be seen as a special case where the number of polygonal faces tends to infinity. This serves as a foundation for deriving the moments of inertia for prisms with a finite number of faces. We then proceed to derive and generalize the formulas for the moments of inertia of regular n-sided polygonal prisms, considering both solid and hollow cases.

2 Inertia for a Cylinder; $n = \infty$

The model for any theoretical moment of inertia must be derived by integrating an infinitesimal measure of mass multiplied by the squared distance to the centroidal axis over the prism's volume [1], expressed as:

$$I = \int r^2 dm \quad (1)$$

Here, the mass "slice" dm can be expressed in terms of volume V and density ρ :

$$dm = \rho \cdot dV \quad (2)$$

Figure 1: Perpendicular centroidal moment of inertia of a cylinder

Assuming the triangular prism has a constant density. At this point, it is easier to first consider the instance of a cylinder, where either face is the circumcircle of the initial triangular prism face (Figure 1). The small volume element dV could therefore be expressed as:

$$dV = r' dr' d\theta dh' \quad (3)$$

Where r' is the radial distance from the axis of rotation, θ is the azimuthal angle, and h' is the height along the cylinder from 0 to h , the maximum height of the cylinder/prism. Using the new definition of volume V as a function of these three variables, (2) can be combined with (3) to yield:

$$I_{cylinder} = \int_0^h \int_0^{2\pi} \int_0^r \rho r'^3 dr' d\theta dh \quad (4)$$

This integral can easily be simplified:

$$I_{cylinder} = \rho \cdot h \cdot 2\pi \cdot \frac{r^4}{4}$$

And solved by substituting $\rho = \frac{m}{V} = \frac{m}{\pi r^2 h}$:

$$I_{cylinder} = \frac{m}{\pi r^2 h} \cdot h \cdot 2\pi \cdot \frac{r^4}{4}$$

$$I_{cylinder} = \frac{1}{2} m r^2 \quad (5)$$

3 Inertia for a Triangular Prism; $n = 3$

Triangle prism is the lowest value so it tells us our lower bound for the function etc. A triangular prism is the lowest possible resolution for the n-gon, so it dictates the lower bound of the inertia function such that $n \in \mathbb{Z}, n \geq 3$.

Figure 2: Variables for integrating the moment of the triangular prism in pieces

All units used in this derivation are marked in Figure 2. To apply a similar derivation to the triangular prism, the integral must be split into three equal parts, as shown in Figure 2. This can be done as total inertia is defined as the sum of inertia contributions by each slice of mass in a geometry [2]. On the smaller triangle, the maximum integration bound r is varied to reflect the distance from the centroid of the triangle to its edge at angle θ , over which the rest of the integrand can be integrated (Figure 2). This smaller triangle will also loop over a third of the initial maximum azimuthal angle (the elliptical will complete only a third-turn). Using this geometry, the total inertia of the triangular prism is defined as:

$$I = 3 \cdot \int_0^h \int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{3}} \int_0^{\left(\frac{r}{2 \sin\left(\theta - \frac{5\pi}{6}\right)}\right)} \rho r'^3 dr' d\theta dh' \quad (6)$$

The following steps can be taken to simplify and solve the integral:

$$\begin{aligned} I &= h \cdot 3 \cdot \int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{3}} \int_0^{\left(\frac{r}{2 \sin\left(\theta - \frac{5\pi}{6}\right)}\right)} \rho r'^3 dr' d\theta \\ I &= h \cdot 3 \cdot \int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{3}} \frac{r^4 \rho}{64 \sin^4\left(\theta + \frac{\pi}{6}\right)} d\theta \\ I &= h \cdot 3 \cdot \frac{r^4 \rho}{64} \int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{3}} \frac{1}{\sin^4\left(\theta + \frac{\pi}{6}\right)} d\theta \end{aligned}$$

Solving this definitely:

$$h \cdot 3 \cdot \frac{r^4 \rho}{64} \cdot 4\sqrt{3}$$

Redefining ρ in terms of m and V :

$$\frac{6\sqrt{3}hr^4m}{32V}$$

Solving for volume as defined by a triangular prism:

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{4 \cdot 6\sqrt{3}hr^4m}{32 \cdot 3\sqrt{3}r^2h} \\ &\frac{4 \cdot 6r^2m}{32 \cdot 3} \end{aligned}$$

Which simplifies to the final equation for the triangular prism's moment of inertia (independent of height) about the centroidal axis:

$$\frac{1}{4}mr^2 \quad (7)$$

This derivation is the most intuitive, but can also be achieved by evaluating the triangular prism as three equally spaced point masses of $\frac{1}{3}m$ at the midpoints of each triangle edge as well as using perpendicular axis theorem (where each perpendicular axis' centroidal moment is $\frac{1}{8}mr^2$) [3].

4 Generalization of Expression

To generalize the equation for the moment of inertia of a regular n-sided prism, a similar technique can be used with a modular upper integration bound depending on the geometry of the given face shape and the circumradius.

For an integral of the following form determining the moment of inertia:

$$I(n) = n \cdot \int_0^h \int_0^\phi \int_0^d \frac{m}{Ah} r'^3 dr' d\theta dh' \quad (8)$$

The following variables can be determined from the number of faces n :

$$\begin{aligned} \beta &= \frac{(n-2)\pi}{2n} \\ \phi &= \frac{2\pi}{n} \\ A &= \frac{ns^2}{4 \tan \frac{\pi}{n}} \end{aligned}$$

The inscribed distance d used for the upper limit of integration is also defined with the circumradius:

$$d = \frac{\sin(\pi - \beta - \theta)}{\sin \beta} r$$

And the side length s is defined as:

$$s = 2r \cos \beta$$

This gives the final generalized integral form (cancelling out height; $\frac{1}{h}$ is a constant term in the integrand):

$$I(n) = n \cdot \int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{n}} \int_0^{\frac{\sin \beta}{\sin(\pi - \beta - \theta)} r} \frac{mr'^3 4 \tan \frac{\pi}{n}}{ns^2} dr' d\theta \quad (9)$$

Which solves as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} I(n) &= n \cdot \int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{n}} \frac{\sin^4(\beta) m \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{n}\right) r^4}{ns^2 \sin^4(\theta + \beta)} d\theta \\ I(n) &= n \cdot \int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{n}} \frac{\sin^4\left(\frac{(n-2)\pi}{2n}\right) m \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{n}\right) r^4}{ns^2 \sin^4\left(\theta + \frac{(n-2)\pi}{2n}\right)} d\theta \\ I(n) &= n \cdot \frac{2m \tan^2\left(\frac{\pi}{n}\right) (\tan^2\left(\frac{\pi}{n}\right) + 3) \sin^4\left(\frac{\pi(n-2)}{2n}\right) r^4}{3ns^2} \end{aligned}$$

And simplifies to the final expression:

$$I(n) = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{n}\right) + 2}{6} mr^2 \quad (10)$$

This equation agrees with our previously derived forms. For a triangular prism ($n = 3$):

$$I(3) = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{3}\right) + 2}{6}mr^2 = \frac{1}{4}mr^2$$

And as $n \rightarrow \infty$ for a cylinder:

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} I(n) = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \frac{\cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{n}\right) + 2}{6}mr^2 = \frac{1}{2}mr^2$$

$\frac{1}{mr^2}I(n)$ can be plotted as a continuous function for $n \geq 3$, where this limit is visually apparent.

Figure 3: Plot of $I(n)$ to visually demonstrate the limit $\frac{1}{2}mr^2$

5 Hollow Prisms

For a given n -sided regular polygonal prism with a circular hole in it (as might be attached to an axle), the same integral can be solved with a lower limit of integration r_i and simplified as follows:

$$I(n) = n \cdot \int_0^h \int_0^{\frac{2\pi}{n}} \int_{r_i}^{\frac{\sin \beta}{\sin(\pi - \beta - \theta)}r} \frac{4 \tan\left(\frac{\pi}{n}\right) m}{ns^2h} r'^3 dr' d\theta dh$$

$$I(n) = \frac{m \left(nr^4 \cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{n}\right) + 2nr^4 - \frac{6\pi r_i^4}{\sin\left(\frac{2\pi}{n}\right)} \right)}{6nr^2}$$

Where $\beta = \frac{(n-2)\pi}{2n}$ and r_i is the inradius of the polygonal face such that $r_i < r \cos \frac{\pi}{n}$ for a given radius and n -gon.

6 Conclusion

This study has derived the moments of inertia for regular n -dimensional polygonal prisms about their centroidal axes. Starting from the well-documented case of the cylindrical prism (where n approaches infinity), the expression for the moment of inertia was successfully generalized to accommodate prisms with a finite number of faces. The derived formula $I(n) = \frac{\cos\left(\frac{2\pi}{n}\right) + 2}{6}mr^2$ provides a straightforward method to calculate the moment of inertia for any regular n -sided polygonal prism.

Additionally, the moments of inertia for hollow prisms were explored, extending the analysis to account for the inner radius. These results are significant as they fill a gap in the existing literature, offering a comprehensive set of formulas

Moment of Inertia for Regular n-Dimensional Polygonal Prism

for both solid and hollow regular polygonal prisms. The findings have practical implications for engineering and physics, particularly in the study of the rotational dynamics of complex shapes.

The provided table of values for standard prisms serves as a useful reference for introductory experiments and theoretical studies. Future work could explore the moments of inertia for irregular prisms and other non-prismatic polyhedra, further expanding the applicability of these methods.

References

- [1] Three-dimensional Hollow Figures. Spheres, Cylinders, Cones, aug 7 2022. [Online; accessed 2024-03-12].
- [2] Moments of Inertia of Some Simple Shapes, aug 7 2022. [Online; accessed 2024-03-12].
- [3] Perpendicular-axis Theorem for Plane Laminae, dec 30 2020. [Online; accessed 2024-03-16].

Appendix

Centroidal Moments of Various Polygonal Prisms		
Triangular Prism ($n = 3$)	Square Prism ($n = 4$)	Pentagonal Prism ($n = 5$)
Simplified: $\frac{1}{4}mr^2$ Approximate: 0.2500	Simplified: $\frac{1}{3}mr^2$ Approximate: 0.3333	Simplified: $\left(\frac{\sqrt{5}}{24} + \frac{7}{24}\right)mr^2$ Approximate: 0.3848
Hexagonal Prism ($n = 6$)	Octagonal Prism ($n = 8$)	Decagonal Prism ($n = 10$)
Simplified: $\frac{5}{12}mr^2$ Approximate: 0.4167	Simplified: $\left(\frac{\sqrt{2}}{12} + \frac{1}{3}\right)mr^2$ Approximate: 0.4512	Simplified: $\left(\frac{\sqrt{5}}{24} + \frac{3}{8}\right)mr^2$ Approximate: 0.4682
Dodecagonal Prism ($n = 12$)	Pentadecagonal Prism ($n = 15$)	Icosagonal Prism ($n = 20$)
Simplified: $\left(\frac{\sqrt{3}}{12} + \frac{1}{3}\right)mr^2$ Approximate: 0.4777	Simplified: $\left(\frac{\sqrt{5}}{48} + \frac{\sqrt{30-6\sqrt{5}}}{48} + \frac{17}{48}\right)mr^2$ Approximate: 0.4856	Simplified: $\left(\frac{\sqrt{2\sqrt{5}+10}}{24} + \frac{1}{3}\right)mr^2$ Approximate: 0.4918